

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Ceres Science Approach (CSA) (vir_da222)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da222 session. These operations were executed as part of the CSA phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Ceres, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da222 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis et al., "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_csa_OpNav_005.r06.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_csa_OpNav_005.r06.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_csa_OpNav_005.r06.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CSA_YMLSTART_OpNav_005	478514214	478514216	2
VIR_CSA_OpNav5PowerOn_001	478514274	478514695	421
VIR_CSA_OpNav5FullCalibration_001	478514874	478527491	12617
VIR_CSA_OpNav5OpenCover_001	478527834	478527874	40
VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_001	478527954	478530828	2874
VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_002	478530834	478533874	3040
VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_003	478533894	478535722	1828
VIR_CSA_OpNav5CryocoolerOff_001	478535724	478535731	7
VIR_CSA_OpNav5CloseCover_001	478552674	478552712	38
VIR_CSA_OpNav5DumpDataToVR4_001	478562514	478572414	9900
VIR_CSA_OpNav5PowerOff_001	478574874	478575174	300
VIR_CSA_YMLEND_OpNav_005	478575294	478575295	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Integrated sequence: da222b.01.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da222b.01.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 3 cubes for IR channel and 3 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

3. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

3.1 The sequence: vir_csa_OpNav_005.r06.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$MARK$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_csa_OpNav_005.r06.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2015-057T08:35:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2015-084T07:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2015-037T11:44:22.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_csa_OpNav_005.r06;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$MARK$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Fri Feb 06 11:44:22 2015
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2015-057T08:35:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2015-084T07:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_CSA_da222_OpNav5_ds233
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CSA_OPNAV_005, 2015-061T00:32:54.000
26 *EPOCHS_END
27 *Input files used:
28 *File Type  Last modified          File name
29 *****
30 $$EOH
31 $$EOD
32
33 request(VIR_CSA_VMLSTART_OpNav_005,
34         START_TIME, CSA_OPNAV_005-03:56:00,
  
```

```

35     TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_csa_OpNav_005 (ds233)",
36     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
37     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
38     KEY, "No_Key")
39
40     activity(1,
41         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
42         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds233","ds233.mc
         fb05")
43     ),
44     note(1,
45         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
46         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds233 - vir_csa_OpNav_005"\
47     ),
48 end;
49
50 request(VIR_CSA_OpNav5PowerOn_001,
51     START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005-03:55:00,
52     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
53     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
54     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
55     KEY, "No_Key")
56
57     spawn(1,
58         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
59         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
60         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
61     ),
62     note(1,
63         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
64         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5PowerOn_001: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
65     ),
66 end;
67
68 request(VIR_CSA_OpNav5FullCalibration_001,
69     START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005-03:45:00,
70     TITLE, "VIR cooldown and full calibration sequence",
71     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
72     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
73     KEY, "No_Key")
74
75     spawn(1,
76         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
77         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
78         RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)
79     ),
80     command(1,
81         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
82         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5FullCalibration_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
83         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
84     ),
85     note(1,
86         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
87         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5FullCalibration_001: Full Calibration VML is finished."\<
88     ),
89     note(2,
90         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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91     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5FullCalibration_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960
92     packets." \
93   ),
94   end;
95   request(VIR_CSA_0pNav50penCover_001,
96     START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005-00:09:00,
97     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
98     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
99     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
100    KEY, "No_Key")
101
102    activity(1,
103      SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
104      NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav50penCover_001: Set for opening the cover." \,
105      VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
106    ),
107  end;
108
109  request(VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_001,
110    START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005-00:07:00,
111    TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
112    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
113    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
114    KEY, "No_Key")
115
116    command(1,
117      SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
118      NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_001: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA,
119      SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA to perform 164 scan mirror steps" \,
120      VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-369000,364500,4500)
121    ),
122    command(2,
123      SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
124      NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,166
125      frame,17 RepTime,Integration time IR=12.000s VIS=8.000s" \,
126      VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",17,165,600,5,400,105,166,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO
127    ),
128    command(3,
129      SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
130      COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.449" \,
131      NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
132      VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
133    ),
134    command(4,
135      SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:47:38\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
136      NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
137      VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
138    ),
139    note(1,
140      SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
141      TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.578 Gibit" \
142    ),
143  end;
144  request(VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_002,
145    START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+00:41:00,

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145     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
146     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
147     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
148     KEY, "No_Key")
149
150     command(1,
151         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
152         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_002: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA,
153         SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA to perform 164 scan mirror steps"\,
154         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-369000,364500,4500)
155     ),
156     command(2,
157         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,166
159         frame,18 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.000s VIS=15.000s"\,
160         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",18,165,100,330,750,5,166,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO
161     ),
162     command(3,
163         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
164         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.449"\,
165         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
166         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
167     ),
168     command(4,
169         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:50:24\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
170         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
171         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
172     ),
173     note(1,
174         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
175         TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.155 Gibit"\
176     ),
177 end;
178
179 request(VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_003,
180     START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+01:32:00,
181     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
182     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
183     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
184     KEY, "No_Key")
185
186     command(1,
187         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
188         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_003: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA,
189         SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA to perform 146 scan mirror steps"\,
190         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-328500,324000,4500)
191     ),
192     command(2,
193         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
194         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_OpNav5CubeToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,148
195         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=9.000s VIS=7.000s"\,
196         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,147,450,5,350,55,148,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO
197     ),
198     command(3,
199         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
200         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.449"\,

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```

197     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
198     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
199   ),
200   command(4,
201     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:30:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
202     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
203     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
204   ),
205   note(1,
206     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
207     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CubeToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.670 Gibit"\
208   ),
209 end;
210
211 request(VIR_CSA_0pNav5CryocoolerOff_001,
212   START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+02:02:30,
213   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
214   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
215   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
216   KEY, "No_Key")
217
218   command(1,
219     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
220     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
221     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
222   ),
223   command(2,
224     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\",
226     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
227   ),
228   note(1,
229     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
230     TEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off."\"
231   ),
232 end;
233
234 request(VIR_CSA_0pNav5CloseCover_001,
235   START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+06:45:00,
236   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
237   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
238   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
239   KEY, "No_Key")
240
241   activity(1,
242     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
243     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CSA_0pNav5CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover."\",
244     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
245   ),
246 end;
247
248 request(VIR_CSA_0pNav5DumpDataToVR4_001,
249   START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+09:29:00,
250   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
251   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
252   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
253   KEY, "No_Key")

```

```
254
255     command(1,
256         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
257         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.690"\,
258         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSA_0pNav5DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
259         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
260     ),
261     command(2,
262         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:44:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CSA_0pNav5DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
264         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
265     ),
266     note(1,
267         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
268         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSA_0pNav5DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.000 Gibit."\
269     ),
270 end;
271
272 request(VIR_CSA_0pNav5PowerOff_001,
273     START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+12:55:00,
274     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
275     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
276     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
277     KEY, "No_Key")
278
279     note(1,
280         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
281         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSA_0pNav5PowerOff_001: Power off VIR instrument."\
282     ),
283     spawn(1,
284         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
285         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
286         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
287     ),
288     note(2,
289         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
290         TEXT,\\"VIR_CSA_0pNav5PowerOff_001: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
291     ),
292 end;
293
294 request(VIR_CSA_VMLEND_0pNav_005,
295     START_TIME,CSA_OPNAV_005+13:02:00,
296     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_csa_0pNav_005 (ds233)",
297     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
298     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
299     KEY, "No_Key")
300
301     note(1,
302         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
303         TEXT,\\"END OF SEQUENCE: ds233 - vir_csa_0pNav_005"\
304     ),
305 end;
306
307 $$EOF
```